

CLOSING THE CHARITY

The Story of
Public Health Pathways

● ● ○ Public
● ○ ● Health
○ ● ● Pathways

2020
2024

Table
Of
Our

Story

Opening move		Act II. Co-creation	16
Board reflections	3	Feature: Pathfinders - case study	17
The membership	4	Community innovation	21
Introduction	6	SMiLES Maternal health project	22
Act I. Listening	7	Fieldwork	24
Videos	8	Values	26
Events	9	Act III. Knowing when to step back	27
Reports	11	Timeline of the charity	28
Rebranding	14	The AGM	30
The Magazine	15	Final quote	31

Board reflections

When I was invited to Chair this group, I learned much from what Public Health Pathways (PHP) were already doing and what you were applying. The key elements were listening to and reflecting on what people were saying. It's effective in a very short time, to the point that others adopt it, and it's interesting to see how your methodology has been absorbed into how other entities work. To me, that is success.

Alan Court

Chair

PHP took an interdisciplinary approach to dealing with complex societal problems. It was not only about having discussions. It was also putting that into practice. It's beautiful to see how an idea can take such a concrete form and not just remain an embryo but come into being. I reflect on its inspiring evolution with pride, admiration, and sheer gratitude for having been on this amazing journey.

Ria Sen

Trustee

I was attracted to PHP because it was an organic response to a need. The group came together without a 'perfect blueprint', but a curiosity to find out where the energy is and what communities want. That sense of respect and humility has permeated all of PHP's work and created a genuinely global movement far beyond the formal charity structure. This means that the seeds sown by PHP will continue growing and thriving in ways we can't imagine today.

Lakshmi Sundaram

Trustee

PHP has shown a path forward where a community of practitioners and civil society members around the world come together. The charity has improved health outcomes through knowledge sharing, fostering collaboration among local communities and between countries, providing technical expertise and dialogue, and advocating for evidence-based care. Congratulations to the entire PHP team for an incredible job.

Borja Santos

Trustee

A story of global impact

Key:	Page:
● PHP Community	5
● Events and speakers	9-11
● Trend reports	11-13
● Fieldwork projects	16-24
● Strategic support	22

Membership

The Public Health Pathways community expanded to encompass 31 countries from diverse ethnic backgrounds. At our heart lay diversity of experience and expertise. With over 85% of members holding master's degrees, they combined expertise from healthcare, humanitarian work, academia, and other innovation-driven backgrounds. They came together to discover, create, and shape healthier futures.

“Diversity and collaboration are essential to developing sustainable strategies for adaptation - both in scientific research and unifying mechanisms that push human evolution.”

- Dr Camila Pang
 Royal Society Science Book of the Year 2020 recipient, speaking to our launch in 2020.

Countries represented:

Europe	Asia	Africa	Latin America
France	China	Cameroon	Brazil
Germany	India	Ethiopia	Colombia
Italy	Lebanon	Eritrea	Mexico
Poland	Saudi Arabia	Ghana	Peru
Russia	Singapore	Nigeria	
Serbia	South Korea	Sudan	North America
Spain	Sri Lanka	Uganda	Bermuda
Switzerland	UAE		Canada
UK			USA

Members list

The faces that built PHP

		Vlada			
				Beatrice	
Virgi					
Patricia					
Belén					
Adam					
Ana Clara					
Boris					
Theo					
Jahlani					
Joe					
Charlotte					
Anushka					
Abigail					

Introduction

So grateful to be part of building Public Health Pathways (PHP) among an incredible community of volunteers. A community concerned with finding a constructive way forward from the start of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The people who started PHP found a way forward by converting the anxiety the pandemic created into a life energy rather than a symptom of illness. We started with a question that gave us impetus: was the public being listened to?

To address this we began by listening to one another as we shared challenges, processed the complexity, and identified gaps in our understanding. We used these data to guide who and how we engaged with information sources and social networks. We focused on listening and learning from the lived experiences of those on the margins to define health's social, political, and economic inequalities.

In practice, PHP sought to avoid marginalisation, be local and global, not judgemental, open, and be with people to facilitate paths forward. Being with people drew us to one of our central values. Critically driven – aim to bridge your lived experiences to build on the best science we know at the time. That provided an edge to our work, where we collaborate, innovate, and co-create alongside communities to make society healthier.

After listening. After co-creation. We asked when the right time to step away was. We learnt that recognising our interdependence gives others the agency to take the initiative. So, in December 2023, at our AGM, the volunteers and trustees who built the charity agreed that PHP had fulfilled its purpose. We concluded that once the impact is absorbed, we step back. We stepped back from PHP, knowing the next generation would take the methodology to new levels.

Enjoy the PHP story.

Theo Richardson-Gool

Public Health Pathways member
and former CEO

“I believe that we have lost the art of listening, and it starts right from the family. Into the community. Into the street. The city, and country, and at the international level.”

- Dr Mohamed Keshavjee
Speaking during the PHP live event,
Mediation in the Present Moment

Act 1

Listening

Act I. Listening	7
Videos	8
Events	9
Reports	11
Rebranding	14
The Magazine	15

Did you know

Public Health Pathways work was televised in two countries. China following the only event we did in Chinese, with Mr Guo Yin (郭因), a 95-year-old Distinguished Philosopher of Aesthetics. Additionally, following a documentary led by PHP member K. Jade Robinson in Bermuda and edited by Adrian Holgate in the UK, the small Island nation's Premiere came on national TV to commend volunteers' marvellous work in supporting their community.

Video hub

Between March and May 2020, PHP published over 20 original videos. These videos offered insights into the human impact and provided advice to guide us through the early months of the pandemic.

The videos covered ethical and health dimensions:

- Eye-witness reports - from the initial impact in Italy.
- Guidance from a South Korean student, "keep calm and follow instructions".
- How do we safeguard against the potential of domestic violence arising during the lockdown? - recorded in Singapore
- Medical advice - Nurse based in France.
- Explainer on how disease spread occurs - Sudanese doctor
- How public health systems respond - video from Australia.
- Balancing attending a Black Lives Matter protest safely - Londoner
- The upheaval of lockdown measures - citizen in India.

"Public Health Pathways is the voice of the public"

- Ester Ogun, PHP founding Pathfinder

Live events i

We hosted ten outstanding live events, where 27 guest speakers influenced our thinking and strategy.

Some organisations our guest speakers worked for:

9 April 2020
We are all in this together

Dr Patricia Gabaldon
Dr Ilan Kelman
Dr Camilla Pang
Yemi Babington-Ashaye

30 April 2020
Looking to the future

Dr Ameenah Gurib-Fakim
Dr Velislava Petrova
Dr. Borja Santos

28 May 2020
Our green future

Anders Wijkman
Ria Sen
Martha McPherson

18 June 2020
Mediation in the present

Prof. Albie Sachs
Dr Mohamed Keshavjee

30 July 2020
Beyond medicine

Dr Nisreen Alwan
Dr Jacob Stegenga
Dr Shireen Kassam

"Be better than us"

- Justice, Albie Sachs

PHP asked Albie for advice on how young people should proceed. He said, "Don't look to us for advice", "Be cheeky, Be Irreverent," and "Take out the bad from what we've done and be better than us", but "You have to find your own way."

Live events ii

8 November 2020
Green Health
(in Chinese)

Mr Guo Yin (郭因)

12 November 2020
Innovation in health

Amel Najjar
Dr Ernest Madu
Dr Tracy Chantler

26 November 2020
Neglected diseases

Prof. Amina Jindani
Prof. Tom Harrison
Dr Nadia Ahmed

19 May 2021
Health is wealth

Samira Khan
Lakshmi Sundaram
Alan Court

23 June 2022
Humanizing Medicine

Prof. Azim Jiwani
Prof. David Nabarro

“As a member of the public, I found myself able to follow the information given by each speaker. It certainly helped that everyone spoke in plain English !! The efforts put in by your team of volunteers who have all strived to deliver some truly remarkable webinars during our Lockdown periods.”

- Nur-Begum Karim
Event viewer

Trend reports i

We meticulously curated 53 trend reports sourced from reputable journals, United Nations agencies, and non-partisan think tanks.

Covering topics from disease outbreaks in Congo to logistical challenges in vaccine delivery, our reports explored WHO funding mechanisms, food insecurity, and historical developments like the 1918 Flu.

As a conduit, our team aimed to equip the public and practitioners worldwide with the latest insights and research analysis.

“I enjoyed working with PHP’s diverse and dedicated team over 30 different countries – one of its most valuable assets, which allowed us to develop more wholesome, context-aware content.”

- Alicia Ramos
Editor at Public Health Pathways

Impact case study

In the 2020 report titled "Language Barriers Leave 1000s in The Can - Can This Be Solved?", A. Ashni revealed that Google's translator distorted "autism" in English to "selfish-p***k" in Hindi. After reported this, Google corrected the error.

Trend reports ii

Published on Public Health Pathways first year: April 2020 to March 2021

How Will The COVID-19 Pandemic Continue? By Alex Erquicia, 24 04 2020

Why Ethnic Minority And Indigenous Communities May Be More At Risk From COVID-19, 12 05 2020

Why A “Green” Economic Recovery Post COVID-19 Is Essential By Alicia Ramos, 5 06 2020

Economic Impacts Of Covid-19 In The Gulf Cooperation Council By Farzana Hussain, 25 04 2020

How Cheap Oil May Expose A Disparity Of Opportunity - By Cristobal Sapena, 12 05 2020

Severe Food Insecurity Predicted Post COVID-19 By Jessie Karlovich, 12 06 2020

UNWTO Leads The Global Tourism Crisis Committee By Belén Ramírez Llopis, 26 04 2020

The World Health Organization Is Central To Public Health Yet Its Funding Is Precariously Balanced By Alex Erquicia, 25 05 2020

Social Justice, Public Health, And Mediation By Jessie Karlovich, Samia Khan, 1 07 2020

“Leave No One Behind” How Will Refugee Communities Cope With COVID-19 By Samia Khan, 26 04 2020

Running Against Time: COVID-19 In The Central Amazon By Iman Hameed, 18 05 2020

Sustaining Life Below Water: The Contrasting Impact Of COVID-19 On Sea Life By Iman Hameed, 1 07 2020

A Story Of A Proactive, Constructive Global Response To COVID-19 By Theo Richardson-Gool, 29 04 2020

SDG 6 And Water, Sanitation & Hygiene: Crucial Against COVID-19 By Jessie Karlovich, 26 05 2020

Yemen: A Country Besieged Confronts COVID-19 By Jessie Karlovich, 3 07 2020

Lessons From Singapore’s Pandemic Response To Marginalised Groups By Iman Hameed, 30 04 2020

Re-Imagining Cities Post COVID-19 By Samia Khan, 29 05 2020

‘No Area Has Been Spared By The Effects Of The Virus.’ United Nations, 10 07 2020

Contrasting Impacts Of COVID-19 On The Environment And Considerations For The Future By Alicia Ramos, 7 05 2020

Children At Risk Of Disease As COVID-19 Impacts Routine Immunisation By Nkengfua Blaise, 3 06 2020

The Congo Besieged: COVID 19, Measles, And An Eleventh Ebola Outbreak By Jessie Karlovich, 17 07 2020

The 1918 Flu Pandemic And COVID-19: History Does Not Repeat Itself, But Often Rhymes By Samia Khan, 21 07 2020

Trend reports iii

Continued: Published on Public Health Pathways first year: April 2020 to March 2021

Migrant Workers In Russia Face An Unsettling Dilemma By Taisiya Patukhova, 27 07 2020

Vaccine Hesitancy Identified As A Top 10 Threat To Global Health By The WHO By Charlotte Bexson, 27 07 2020

Biodiversity In Crisis: Building Back Better By Jessie Karlovich, Samia Khan, 11 08 2020

COVID-19 Health Inequalities, Diet, And Non-Pharmacological Intervention By Michael Baser, Charlotte Bexson, Iman Hameed, 11 08 2020

Interpreting COVID-19 Dreams By Adriana Michalak, 17 08 2020

How Can We Look After Those Who Look After Us? By Bryony Porter, 28 08 2020

Beirut Explosion: Four Recommendations To Curb The Public Health Impact By Samia Khan, 4 09 2020

John Snow's Disease Mapping Strategy: From Cholera To COVID-19 By Nkengfua Blaise, 9 09 2020

Language Barrier Leaves 1000s In The Dark – Can This Be Solved? By A. Ashni, 16 09 2020

Neuro-COVID-19: Complications That Call For Ongoing Analysis And Research By Adriana Michalak, 17 09 2020

Four Distinct Acts Of Infectious Disease Outbreaks By Charlotte Bexson, 22 09 2020

The Public Health Legacy Of Florence Nightingale: A Lesson For COVID-19 Recovery By Michael Baser, 7 10 2020

Investing In Tomorrows Citizens: Five

Recommendations For Early Childhood Education By Samia Khan, 27 10 2020

Waldemar Haffkine: "The Most Unfamous Man..." Behind Vaccine Development, By Taisiya Patukhova, 20 11 2020

Critical Vaccine Delivery: A Challenge For The Global South By Iman Hameed, 22 12 2020

Public Health Innovation & Vaccine Confidence By Charlotte Bexson, 22 12 2020

Is The COVID-19 Pandemic Leading To A Mental Health Crisis? By Vlada Shevelkova, 12 01 2021

Tourisms Worst Year Prompts A Call For Safe And Sustainable Travel By Belén Ramírez Llopis, 1 02 2021

Losing My Father To COVID-19 By Ashley Rhoden, 8 02 2021

How Are Vaccines Developed? Why So Many? And Why Is The WTO Involved? By Ana Clara De Queiroz, 19 03 2021

Loneliness – The Silent Pandemic By Adriana Michalak, 3 03 2021

"I was very proud to see the report published on the PHP public website platform where it is available as grey literature, showcasing the breadth of field work undertaken"

Michael Baser
- PHP Editorial strategist and trend reporter

Rebranding

Retracing the process to rebrand from Cov360 to Public Health Pathways.

Reflecting on the rebranding journey, I see it as a transformative milestone in our charity's development.

From reactive growth during the pandemic to a proactive mindset looking to broader health determinants, the updated name and branding embodied our mission and values. The process of achieving this was an incredibly rewarding challenge, which I am grateful to have shared with Public Health Pathways.

*- Alec Strobel
Designer at Public Health Pathways*

Our Magazine

After rebranding we published our magazine in August 2021 The Age of Public Health, that outlined our vision:

A world in which all generations can discover, create, and shape healthier futures.

By this point, we had developed our communications guidelines.

Testimonial:

Culturally, within the black community the pandemic highlighted problems such as trust amongst peers within the health service and mistrust in government guidance. I genuinely believe Public Health Pathways helped to bridge the gap between the communities and misinformation.

- Ashley Rhoden
PHP author and member

Five rules for evidenced communication are:

1. Inform, not persuade
2. Balance, but not false balance
3. Disclose uncertainties
4. State evidence quality
5. Pre-bunk misinformation

Four guidelines for intelligent openness about information:

1. Accessible: people can find it
2. Intelligible: people can understand it
3. Useable: it answers their questions and concerns
4. Assessable: it can be checked and explained

PHP used an evidence-based approach, and the work of Baroness Onora O'Neill and Professor Sir David Spiegelhalter work informed the communications rules and guidelines. Some recommended links to engage O'Neill's [The Reith Lectures: A Question of Trust](#), and Speighalter's [Imperial Lecture: Can we trust the statistics in the media?](#)

"I really appreciate your propositions and practices. We only succeed if all humans love, help, and work together to solve problems. We need organisations like yours."

- Mr Guo Yin (郭因)
95-year-old
Distinguished Philosopher of Aesthetics

Theo asked questions from London at 08h00. Jonathan Zhang translated in Boston at 20h00. Mr Guo Yin answered at 08h00 Hangzhou.

Act 2

Co-creation

Act II. Co-creation	16
Feature: Pathfinders - case study	17
Community innovation	21
SMILES Maternal health project	22
Fieldwork	24
Values	26

Did you know

Beyond fieldwork initiatives, PHP provided strategic assistance to local and grassroots NGOs worldwide. This included advising on mask development during shortages in Trinidad and facilitating logistics for PPE imports into Nigeria. Additionally, PHP supported efforts by distributing translated COVID-19 guidance in Urdu and Arabic to refugee camps in Northern Pakistan and along the Sudanese borders. The charity also offered strategic guidance to an inclusive education school project in Somaliland. These efforts addressed various public health challenges.

Pathfinders

Case study context

NOVEMBER 2020 - NATIONWIDE SURVEY

Almost 500 18-25-year-olds responded to questions on public health and COVID-19 following a collaboration between PHP and Debut. Kim Connor Streich and Avantika Vaishnav gave input and made this possible.

JANUARY 2021 - VOICE OF THE FUTURE REPORT:

71% of respondents felt their voices were not being heard; half did not have access to the necessary support; and 75% highlighted the need for more public health education.

- Concern over misinformation
- Too little public health education
- Poor mental health support

FEBRUARY 2021 - PATHFINDERS PROGRAMME

8 young people

8 sessions
2 months

Held online

Methods:

- Double Diamond
- Applied psychology
- Peer-to-peer learning
- Systems thinking
- Theory of change

Skills we promote:

- Public speaking
- Creativity and initiative
- Empathy and resilience
- Problem-solving
- Project management

Characteristics

- 1-to-1 follow ups
- Co-creation - allowing group to focus on areas of interest or difficulty
- Session summary documents - guide future sessions with reflection and preparation
- Split into interest-specific teams - increase shared affinity, responsibility and accountability
- Speaker sessions to introduce new concepts or inspire action

OUTCOMES

Individual impact:

100% agreed the training was helpful.

Skills developed attributed to various participants achieving new job roles.

Organisational:

The Pathfinders methods informed a broader internal approach, including a workshop involving members that helped guide PHP's strategy development. In 2022, the same methods were used in-person program in Bristol, UK addressed misinformation and homelessness prevention.

PATHFINDERS' PROGRAMME STRATEGIC SUPPORTERS:

Pathfinders

The Case study i

Case Study by Zoë Stockton in collaboration with Naigwe Kalema

SETTING THE STAGE

In November 2020, I completed a survey via Debut looking at the experiences of young people like me during the COVID-19 pandemic. At this point, I had spent 6 months self-isolating with my elderly parents, having moved back home after graduating the previous year. Conversations with friends revolved around pandemic anxieties, frustration with lockdowns, and vaccine hesitancy. There was a pervasive feeling that our most formative years were on pause and held back from what could have been.

The survey inspired me to get involved with PHP, helping to synthesise the outcomes into the Voice of the Future Report. This report highlighted the need for young people to be empowered to lead their own public health initiatives in areas they are concerned about within contexts that impact them.

WHAT CAME NEXT - THE PATHFINDERS PROGRAM

February 2021. In the midst of the third UK lockdown, sitting at my make-shift desk in my parents living room, I started the first session of the Pathfinders Program with 7 others from various backgrounds from across the UK.

How was the Pathfinders Program initiated?

The program started with a relaxed exploration of the issues raised in the survey, with particular emphasis on getting to know one another, listening, and sharing personal experiences. I felt nervous about sharing my opinions, but the friendly, open atmosphere affirmed the value of each of our own thoughts, views, and experiences navigating public health issues as young people.

Whilst each session was structured and moderated by PHP leaders, the co-creation and experimental approach of the program was made clear by focusing on areas of difficulty/interest as they appeared with 1-to-1 check-ins throughout.

What was a key junction during the program?

The first design thinking workshop of the Pathfinders Program represented a key junction for me. I was working as a Mental Health Support Worker for the NHS and had grown frustrated by the lack of holistic preventative approaches in mental health, despite the commonalities in patients, and the increasing focus on distant, number-led approaches to healthcare.

Design thinking gave a name to the interdisciplinary, systems-level methodologies I had been searching for at work, showing the benefits of designing change around people's lived experiences.

"The Pathfinders Program provides a platform for us to determine the future."

Pathfinders

The Case study ii

OUTCOMES - AFTER THE PATHFINDERS PROGRAM

The program had unanimous positive feedback which I attribute to PHP's embedded values.

- *Listening created a safe environment to express our own views and experiences amongst peers. This promoted bonding, engagement and reassured us of our value as young people in public health policy.*
- *Co-creation used a cyclical process of introducing theory, practising new techniques, reflecting on their success and encouraging us to make decisions on what to focus on next.*
- *Giving agency was reflected in allowing individuals to develop our own projects, either within groups or individually, and follow through with these ideas with support from PHP leaders.*

For me, the program was a lifeline in isolation. Meeting new wonderful people, exchanging ideas, and engaging in interesting work, all broadened my worldview and increased my confidence.

KEY LEARNING POINTS FOR ENGAGING YOUTH

- *Emphasising the importance of sharing and listening to individual experiences is powerful. It informs discussion of real-life public health issues and builds strong trust between members.*
- *Combining group engagements with individual follow-ups and smaller breakout groups increased participation.*
- *Breaking up session styles with interesting talks and workshops introducing new concepts keeps engagement high.*
- *Consider the ending the of the program from the start with post-program support and funding options to enable motivated individuals to take their ideas even further.*

"My confidence level has gone up. I now think more clearly. It has helped me in the long term"
- John, 21

The founding Pathfinders from top left: Toby, Theo, Ester, Jameela, John, Priya, Gianluca, Zoe, Becca - who shaped the training.

The training was made possible with input from Gianluca Tomasello, Josh Entsminger, Adam Abdulla, Samia Khan, Jakia Siddique Sufian, Vlada Shevelkova, Alec Strobel.

Pathfinders

Case study legacy

The Pathfinders Programmes were designed by Alec Strobel

Audience listening to a presentation from Ellie and Warsome in St Pauls Bristol on how young people can help tackle misinformation.

The first Bristol Pathfinders focused on tackling misinformation. Ellie went on to facilitate the PHP workshop on systems thinking. With guest talks along the way from around the globe; Iman in Singapore, Jade in Bermuda, Olawale in Nigeria, Patricia in Brazil.

Testimonials:

“The system thinking approach helped address homelessness at its roots and its totality rather than as an isolated social fact”

“Having a systems thinking workshop with professionals and those with lived experience is brilliant and essential in how to move forwards”

Results from the homelessness prevention systems thinking workshop

The Bristol programme was funded through a £5,000 donation from:

Partners for Bristol workshops aimed at tackling misinformation and reducing homelessness:

Community innovation

Interactive meetings were crucial to building the charity. In one notable 60-minute workshop, 16 participants started with a warm-up dance to "Move Your Feet" by Junior Senior (with a dancing team pictured).

"I am really proud of the team. We did everything on time. It was a really nice environment. This workshop was an opportunity to see that we are all part of something bigger."
 - Camila Carbone

"It was definitely fun. I had an amazing team who were able to achieve our goals."
 - Gianluca Tomasello

"I really enjoyed speaking with everyone. Everyone in the group was really excellent. So, thank you."
 - Vlada Shevelkova

The workshop had three teams that provided insights, which we used to create the ecosystem impact map shown below:

"It was super cool, and it's wonderful what we achieved in a short space of time. It was a very good experience."
 - Samia Khan

"What I really like is that we essential are very quick to reach an agreement and very open to listening to each other. Really good workshop."
 - Martina Sungaila Marjanovic

Safe Mothers in Low-income Emergency Settings (SMiLES): Local Community Research Findings

Using “Lay Epidemiology” to evaluate the scope of training traditional birth attendants in South West Cameroon

PHP SMiLES team: Iman Hameed, Camila Carbone, Mariam Jiwani, Boris Mbia, K. Jade Robinson, Michael Baser, Charlotte Bexson, Olawale Adeniyi, Nkengfua Blaise

We partnered with a local NGO to address maternal mortality in Southwest Cameroon using a participatory epidemiological approach. The NGO visited war-impacted ghost towns and engaged with locals through open-ended surveys, collecting data, starting conversations, and exploring collaborative ways to reduce high maternal mortality rates. The trustful relationships built between the community and traditional birth attendants became an opportunity to reduce preventable complications by integrating their work into the formal healthcare system.

“You are on the right path. Research first, understand the reasons”
 In memory, Dr Martina Lukong Baye (2022)

“It has been an honour partnering with PHP. I sincerely thank the entire team for their selfless contributions and the opportunity to collaborate on such important work, which greatly affects the lives of women and, worst of all, in conflict settings.”

Mokwe Welisane Nkeng
 Founder of the Welisane Foundation

The SMiLES report

Safe Mothers in Low-income Emergency Settings (SMiLES): Local Community Research Findings

Using "Lay Epidemiology" to evaluate the scope of training traditional birth attendants in Cameroon

In memory of Dr. Martina Lukong Baye, who passed away in July 2022.

"You are on the right path. Research first. Understand the reasons."

These were the guiding words of the former Coordinator of the National Multi-sector Programme to Combat Maternal, Newborn and Child Mortality, in Cameroon, and early advisor and supporter of the SMiLES project. Dr Baye shaped the project focus on community engagement and expert-informed training.

Report and research funded by:

Ashworth Charitable Trust and the generosity of Limahl Mair-Macfarlane and Philmon Habtai made this research possible.

Click to access the report:

"My hope is SMiLES will grow to integrate clinic and community, that it can in future provide continued antenatal care by linking clinic staff, Traditional Birth Attendants and women through low-resource communication interventions to overcome the barriers women are facing in accessing antenatal care due to the conflict"

- Iman Hameed
SMiLES Strategic Lead

Research funded through a grant from Ashworth Charitable Trust, with donations from Philmon Habtai and Limahl Macfarlane. Thank you.

Fieldwork i

Knowledge Transfer Exchange

In the final years of the charity’s existence it dedicated itself to understanding health inequalities, one community at a time. From one community to another their was a knowledge transfer exchange.

Maternal health in Cameroon from 2021 to date

Co-designed through community-led data gathering an intervention to reduce maternal mortality by training traditional birth attendants.

Research funded by the Ashworth Charitable Trust

Inner city health access in the UK in 2022

From Cameroon we co-learnt and developed impact measurement for a Somali-led community clinic in Bristol to evidence and co-lead advocacy.

Consultancy position funded by the NHS

Bermuda heart and prostate health in 2023

Using methods from Cameroon, the UK, sharing evaluation approaches for an initiative that serves uninsured and underinsured men.

Volunteer position supporting its early development

Public Health Pathways aim to build trust by advancing 'health research literacy' and bringing science and lived experience together to humanise medicine.

- **Local collaborations** to work with marginalised groups to assess needs
- **Co-design** community-led interventions to improve health access
- **Co-Learn** alongside communities to measure impact and build trust
- **Co-Lead** advocacy to drive innovation and political and policy commitments that advance equity

Pictured from top: Fieldwork led by the Welisane Foundation in Cameroon. Caafi Health clinic in inner city Bristol. Volunteers in the Bermuda Daily Male clinic.

Fieldwork ii

Case studies

In the UK

Supporting a Bristol-based Caafi Health community clinics with measuring their impact in 2022. A charity led by Huda Hajinur and Asha Mohamed.

PHP helped through:

- Co-designing data collection methods
- Reporting epidemiological data to directly to the regional NHS
- Designing pitch decks and drafting reports

The impact we demonstrated (pictured):

- Data gaps in health disparities
- 97% local buy-in for establishing permanent clinics

Since Caafi Health have gone on to:

- Secured extended funding
- Build links with two University's

Community Clinics
Caafi Health clinics are transforming how we think about community health engagement in Bristol.

Seeing 4 people an hour we average 20 visitors per clinic. The first 19 clinics enabled 377 people to access health services.

From addressing mental health to improving physical health - we provide invaluable services that empower people in areas with high levels of deprivation to manage their wellbeing. We personalise services, from translation to culturally relevant advice, building trust and understanding in our community.

"Without your community clinics, I would have difficulty understanding my prostate cancer." - Iqbal

Our evidence shows we support the Core20PLUS5 [1] strategy:

- 88% of visitors are Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic:**

Ethnicity	Percentage
Black African	50.0%
Black Caribbean	33.0%
South Asian	10.0%
Other	7.0%
- Distribution of visitors with Bristol postcodes (top 85%):**

Postcode	Percentage
BS1 1AA	15.0%
BS1 1AB	12.0%
BS1 1AC	10.0%
BS1 1AD	8.0%
BS1 1AE	7.0%
BS1 1AF	6.0%
BS1 1AG	5.0%
BS1 1AH	4.0%
BS1 1AJ	3.0%
BS1 1AL	2.0%
BS1 1AN	1.0%
BS1 1AP	1.0%
BS1 1AQ	1.0%
BS1 1AR	1.0%
BS1 1AS	1.0%
BS1 1AT	1.0%
BS1 1AU	1.0%
BS1 1AW	1.0%
BS1 1AX	1.0%
BS1 1AY	1.0%
BS1 1AZ	1.0%
BS1 1BA	1.0%
BS1 1BB	1.0%
BS1 1BC	1.0%
BS1 1BD	1.0%
BS1 1BE	1.0%
BS1 1BF	1.0%
BS1 1BG	1.0%
BS1 1BH	1.0%
BS1 1BJ	1.0%
BS1 1BL	1.0%
BS1 1BN	1.0%
BS1 1BP	1.0%
BS1 1BQ	1.0%
BS1 1BR	1.0%
BS1 1BS	1.0%
BS1 1BT	1.0%
BS1 1BU	1.0%
BS1 1BW	1.0%
BS1 1BX	1.0%
BS1 1BY	1.0%
BS1 1BZ	1.0%
BS1 1CA	1.0%
BS1 1CB	1.0%
BS1 1CC	1.0%
BS1 1CD	1.0%
BS1 1CE	1.0%
BS1 1CF	1.0%
BS1 1CG	1.0%
BS1 1CH	1.0%
BS1 1CJ	1.0%
BS1 1CL	1.0%
BS1 1CN	1.0%
BS1 1CP	1.0%
BS1 1CQ	1.0%
BS1 1CR	1.0%
BS1 1CS	1.0%
BS1 1CT	1.0%
BS1 1CU	1.0%
BS1 1CV	1.0%
BS1 1CW	1.0%
BS1 1CX	1.0%
BS1 1CY	1.0%
BS1 1CZ	1.0%
BS1 1DA	1.0%
BS1 1DB	1.0%
BS1 1DC	1.0%
BS1 1DD	1.0%
BS1 1DE	1.0%
BS1 1DF	1.0%
BS1 1DG	1.0%
BS1 1DH	1.0%
BS1 1DJ	1.0%
BS1 1DL	1.0%
BS1 1DN	1.0%
BS1 1DP	1.0%
BS1 1DQ	1.0%
BS1 1DR	1.0%
BS1 1DS	1.0%
BS1 1DT	1.0%
BS1 1DU	1.0%
BS1 1DV	1.0%
BS1 1DW	1.0%
BS1 1DX	1.0%
BS1 1DY	1.0%
BS1 1DZ	1.0%
BS1 1EA	1.0%
BS1 1EB	1.0%
BS1 1EC	1.0%
BS1 1ED	1.0%
BS1 1EE	1.0%
BS1 1EF	1.0%
BS1 1EG	1.0%
BS1 1EH	1.0%
BS1 1EJ	1.0%
BS1 1EL	1.0%
BS1 1EN	1.0%
BS1 1EP	1.0%
BS1 1EQ	1.0%
BS1 1ER	1.0%
BS1 1ES	1.0%
BS1 1ET	1.0%
BS1 1EU	1.0%
BS1 1EV	1.0%
BS1 1EW	1.0%
BS1 1EX	1.0%
BS1 1EY	1.0%
BS1 1EZ	1.0%
BS1 1FA	1.0%
BS1 1FB	1.0%
BS1 1FC	1.0%
BS1 1FD	1.0%
BS1 1FE	1.0%
BS1 1FF	1.0%
BS1 1FG	1.0%
BS1 1FH	1.0%
BS1 1FJ	1.0%
BS1 1FL	1.0%
BS1 1FN	1.0%
BS1 1FP	1.0%
BS1 1FQ	1.0%
BS1 1FR	1.0%
BS1 1FS	1.0%
BS1 1FT	1.0%
BS1 1FU	1.0%
BS1 1FV	1.0%
BS1 1FW	1.0%
BS1 1FX	1.0%
BS1 1FY	1.0%
BS1 1FZ	1.0%
BS1 1GA	1.0%
BS1 1GB	1.0%
BS1 1GC	1.0%
BS1 1GD	1.0%
BS1 1GE	1.0%
BS1 1GF	1.0%
BS1 1GG	1.0%
BS1 1GH	1.0%
BS1 1GJ	1.0%
BS1 1GL	1.0%
BS1 1GN	1.0%
BS1 1GP	1.0%
BS1 1GQ	1.0%
BS1 1GR	1.0%
BS1 1GS	1.0%
BS1 1GT	1.0%
BS1 1GU	1.0%
BS1 1GV	1.0%
BS1 1GW	1.0%
BS1 1GX	1.0%
BS1 1GY	1.0%
BS1 1GZ	1.0%
BS1 1HA	1.0%
BS1 1HB	1.0%
BS1 1HC	1.0%
BS1 1HD	1.0%
BS1 1HE	1.0%
BS1 1HF	1.0%
BS1 1HG	1.0%
BS1 1HH	1.0%
BS1 1HJ	1.0%
BS1 1HL	1.0%
BS1 1HN	1.0%
BS1 1HP	1.0%
BS1 1HQ	1.0%
BS1 1HR	1.0%
BS1 1HS	1.0%
BS1 1HT	1.0%
BS1 1HU	1.0%
BS1 1HV	1.0%
BS1 1HW	1.0%
BS1 1HX	1.0%
BS1 1HY	1.0%
BS1 1HZ	1.0%
BS1 1JA	1.0%
BS1 1JB	1.0%
BS1 1JC	1.0%
BS1 1JD	1.0%
BS1 1JE	1.0%
BS1 1JF	1.0%
BS1 1JG	1.0%
BS1 1JH	1.0%
BS1 1JJ	1.0%
BS1 1JL	1.0%
BS1 1JN	1.0%
BS1 1JP	1.0%
BS1 1JQ	1.0%
BS1 1JR	1.0%
BS1 1JS	1.0%
BS1 1JT	1.0%
BS1 1JU	1.0%
BS1 1JV	1.0%
BS1 1JW	1.0%
BS1 1JX	1.0%
BS1 1JY	1.0%
BS1 1JZ	1.0%
BS1 1KA	1.0%
BS1 1KB	1.0%
BS1 1KC	1.0%
BS1 1KD	1.0%
BS1 1KE	1.0%
BS1 1KF	1.0%
BS1 1KG	1.0%
BS1 1KH	1.0%
BS1 1KJ	1.0%
BS1 1KL	1.0%
BS1 1KN	1.0%
BS1 1KP	1.0%
BS1 1KQ	1.0%
BS1 1KR	1.0%
BS1 1KS	1.0%
BS1 1KT	1.0%
BS1 1KU	1.0%
BS1 1KV	1.0%
BS1 1KW	1.0%
BS1 1KX	1.0%
BS1 1KY	1.0%
BS1 1KZ	1.0%
BS1 1LA	1.0%
BS1 1LB	1.0%
BS1 1LC	1.0%
BS1 1LD	1.0%
BS1 1LE	1.0%
BS1 1LF	1.0%
BS1 1LG	1.0%
BS1 1LH	1.0%
BS1 1LJ	1.0%
BS1 1LL	1.0%
BS1 1LN	1.0%
BS1 1LP	1.0%
BS1 1LQ	1.0%
BS1 1LR	1.0%
BS1 1LS	1.0%
BS1 1LT	1.0%
BS1 1LU	1.0%
BS1 1LV	1.0%
BS1 1LW	1.0%
BS1 1LX	1.0%
BS1 1LY	1.0%
BS1 1LZ	1.0%
BS1 1MA	1.0%
BS1 1MB	1.0%
BS1 1MC	1.0%
BS1 1MD	1.0%
BS1 1ME	1.0%
BS1 1MF	1.0%
BS1 1MG	1.0%
BS1 1MH	1.0%
BS1 1MJ	1.0%
BS1 1ML	1.0%
BS1 1MN	1.0%
BS1 1MP	1.0%
BS1 1MQ	1.0%
BS1 1MR	1.0%
BS1 1MS	1.0%
BS1 1MT	1.0%
BS1 1MU	1.0%
BS1 1MV	1.0%
BS1 1MW	1.0%
BS1 1MX	1.0%
BS1 1MY	1.0%
BS1 1MZ	1.0%
BS1 1NA	1.0%
BS1 1NB	1.0%
BS1 1NC	1.0%
BS1 1ND	1.0%
BS1 1NE	1.0%
BS1 1NF	1.0%
BS1 1NG	1.0%
BS1 1NH	1.0%
BS1 1NJ	1.0%
BS1 1NL	1.0%
BS1 1NN	1.0%
BS1 1NP	1.0%
BS1 1NQ	1.0%
BS1 1NR	1.0%
BS1 1NS	1.0%
BS1 1NT	1.0%
BS1 1NU	1.0%
BS1 1NV	1.0%
BS1 1NW	1.0%
BS1 1NX	1.0%
BS1 1NY	1.0%
BS1 1NZ	1.0%
BS1 1OA	1.0%
BS1 1OB	1.0%
BS1 1OC	1.0%
BS1 1OD	1.0%
BS1 1OE	1.0%
BS1 1OF	1.0%
BS1 1OG	1.0%
BS1 1OH	1.0%
BS1 1OJ	1.0%
BS1 1OL	1.0%
BS1 1ON	1.0%
BS1 1OP	1.0%
BS1 1OQ	1.0%
BS1 1OR	1.0%
BS1 1OS	1.0%
BS1 1OT	1.0%
BS1 1OU	1.0%
BS1 1OV	1.0%
BS1 1OW	1.0%
BS1 1OX	1.0%
BS1 1OY	1.0%
BS1 1OZ	1.0%
BS1 1PA	1.0%
BS1 1PB	1.0%
BS1 1PC	1.0%
BS1 1PD	1.0%
BS1 1PE	1.0%
BS1 1PF	1.0%
BS1 1PG	1.0%
BS1 1PH	1.0%
BS1 1PJ	1.0%
BS1 1PL	1.0%
BS1 1PN	1.0%
BS1 1PP	1.0%
BS1 1PQ	1.0%
BS1 1PR	1.0%
BS1 1PS	1.0%
BS1 1PT	1.0%
BS1 1PU	1.0%
BS1 1PV	1.0%
BS1 1PW	1.0%
BS1 1PX	1.0%
BS1 1PY	1.0%
BS1 1PZ	1.0%
BS1 1QA	1.0%
BS1 1QB	1.0%
BS1 1QC	1.0%
BS1 1QD	1.0%
BS1 1QE	1.0%
BS1 1QF	1.0%
BS1 1QG	1.0%
BS1 1QH	1.0%
BS1 1QJ	1.0%
BS1 1QL	1.0%
BS1 1QN	1.0%
BS1 1QP	1.0%
BS1 1QQ	1.0%
BS1 1QR	1.0%
BS1 1QS	1.0%
BS1 1QT	1.0%
BS1 1QU	1.0%
BS1 1QV	1.0%
BS1 1QW	1.0%
BS1 1QX	1.0%
BS1 1QY	1.0%
BS1 1QZ	1.0%
BS1 1RA	1.0%
BS1 1RB	1.0%
BS1 1RC	1.0%
BS1 1RD	1.0%
BS1 1RE	1.0%
BS1 1RF	1.0%
BS1 1RG	1.0%
BS1 1RH	1.0%
BS1 1RJ	1.0%
BS1 1RL	1.0%
BS1 1RN	1.0%
BS1 1RP	1.0%
BS1 1RQ	1.0%
BS1 1RR	1.0%
BS1 1RS	1.0%
BS1 1RT	1.0%
BS1 1RU	1.0%
BS1 1RV	1.0%
BS1 1RW	1.0%
BS1 1RX	1.0%
BS1 1RY	1.0%
BS1 1RZ	1.0%
BS1 1SA	1.0%
BS1 1SB	1.0%
BS1 1SC	1.0%
BS1 1SD	1.0%
BS1 1SE	1.0%
BS1 1SF	1.0%
BS1 1SG	1.0%
BS1 1SH	1.0%
BS1 1SJ	1.0%
BS1 1SL	1.0%
BS1 1SN	1.0%
BS1 1SP	1.0%
BS1 1SQ	1.0%
BS1 1SR	1.0%
BS1 1SS	1.0%
BS1 1ST	1.0%
BS1 1SU	1.0%
BS1 1SV	1.0%
BS1 1SW	1.0%
BS1 1SX	1.0%
BS1 1SY	1.0%
BS1 1SZ	1.0%
BS1 1TA	1.0%
BS1 1TB	1.0%
BS1 1TC	1.0%
BS1 1TD	1.0%
BS1 1TE	1.0%
BS1 1TF	1.0%
BS1 1TG	1.0%
BS1 1TH	1.0%
BS1 1TJ	1.0%
BS1 1TL	1.0%
BS1 1TN	1.0%
BS1 1TP	1.0%
BS1 1TQ	1.0%
BS1 1TR	1.0%
BS1 1TS	1.0%
BS1 1TT	1.0%
BS1 1TU	1.0%
BS1 1TV	1.0%
BS1 1TW	1.0%
BS1 1TX	1.0%
BS1 1TY	1.0%
BS1 1TZ	1.0%
BS1 1UA	1.0%
BS1 1UB	1.0%
BS1 1UC	1.0%
BS1 1UD	1.0%
BS1 1UE	1.0%
BS1 1UF	1.0%
BS1 1UG	1.0%
BS1 1UH	1.0%
BS1 1UJ	1.0%
BS1 1UL	1.0%
BS1 1UN	1.0%
BS1 1UP	1.0%
BS1 1UQ	1.0%
BS1 1UR	1.0%
BS1 1US	1.0%
BS1 1UT	1.0%
BS1 1UU	1.0%
BS1 1UV	1.0%
BS1 1UW	1.0%
BS1 1UX	1.0%
BS1 1UY	1.0%
BS1 1UZ	1.0%
BS1 1VA	1.0%
BS1 1VB	1.0%
BS1 1VC	1.0%
BS1 1VD	1.0%
BS1 1VE	1.0%
BS1 1VF	1.0%
BS1 1VG	1.0%
BS1 1VH	1.0%
BS1 1VJ	1.0%
BS1 1VL	1.0%
BS1 1VN	1.0%
BS1 1VP	1.0%
BS1 1VQ	1.0%
BS1 1VR	1.0%
BS1 1VS	1.0%
BS1 1VT	1.0%
BS1 1VU	1.0%
BS1 1VV	1.0%
BS1 1VW	1.0%
BS1 1VX	1.0%
BS1 1VY	1.0%
BS1 1VZ	1.0%
BS1 1WA	1.0%
BS1 1WB	1.0%
BS1 1WC	1.0%
BS1 1WD	1.0%
BS1 1WE	1.0%
BS1 1WF	1.0%
BS1 1WG	1.0%
BS1 1WH	1.0%
BS1 1WJ	1.0%
BS1 1WL	1.0%
BS1 1WN	1.0%
BS1 1WP	1.0%
BS1 1WQ	1.0%
BS1 1WR	1.0%
BS1 1WS	1.0%
BS1 1WT	1.0%
BS1 1WU	1.0%
BS1 1WV	1.0%
BS1 1WW	1.0%
BS1 1WX	1.0%
BS1 1WY	1.0%
BS1 1WZ	1.0%
BS1 1XA	1.0%
BS1 1XB	1.0%
BS1 1XC	1.0%
BS1 1XD	1.0%
BS1 1XE	1.0%
BS1 1XF	1.0%
BS1 1XG	1.0%
BS1 1XH	1.0%
BS1 1XJ	1.0%

Values

TRUSTWORTHY

We consistently demonstrate integrity and reliability in all of our actions and interactions.

CRITICALLY DRIVEN

We aim to bridge lived experience to build on the best science we know at the time.

COMMUNITY FOCUSED

We work passionately to advance preventative health measures that build resilience within communities.

INCLUSIVE

We actively listen and understand diverse viewpoints to create effective and equitable solutions.

TRANSFORMATIVE

We strive for structural change by actively promoting technological advances that include diverse perspectives.

On Saturday, December 2, 2023, in London, St Martin-in-the-Fields, I sat with colleagues in the Desmond Tutu room for the final Public Health Pathways meeting. It was the moment when I finally formulated for myself that promoting and giving agency was central to our accomplishments.

I will remember the Public Health Pathways workshop-based way of operating. Dialogue, our primary instrument, allowed us to focus our work on what we learned from the communities we serve, going beyond preconceived ideas. This felt natural for us from the very start, and, first and foremost, it reflected the values we promoted as a charity.

It changed my understanding of charity work. Knowing the Public Health Pathways methodology is out there for others to take the way to new levels, we can step back. I learned that we gain agency by listening to each other, being heard, and co-creating our projects.

- Taisiya Petukhova
- Public Health Pathways volunteer

Act 3

Knowing when to step back

"We send our congratulations to the team at Public Health Pathways. In a short time they achieved a great deal and in particular the training they offered has helped to nurture a workforce more informed about inequalities"

- Prof. Sir Michael Marmot & Dr Tammy Boyce

UCL Institute of Health Equity and supporter of the PHP Pathfinders programme

Act III. Knowing when to step back	27
Timeline of the charity	28
The AGM	30
Final quote	31

Did you know

Public Health Pathways raised just under £10,000 over its lifespan. Despite limited funds, the charity turned down partnerships and funding that didn't align with its values. For instance, the CEO declined donations from an equity firm that clashed with the organisation's climate change stance.

From the start i

When the charity formerly known as Cov360 launched

The smooth launch (irony emoji)

April 9, 2020: Was the launch smooth? *Not at all.*

However, you stay calm and carry on [sort of]. When Facebook Live fails and the host can't hear the panelist on Zoom, you stick together.

Here is to the website builders, involved from before launch 2020 to archiving the website in 2024.

Thank you, Ashish Mehra & Jonathan Uttankar.

Closing event remarks from the Cov360 host:

"We need to and must build communities both biologically through science and societally by changing our behaviour and thinking, taking action together, and ensuring where possible we can mitigate and prepare against future hazards. That is the underlying philosophy of Cov360 as it looks to the future to enhance global well-being to inspire us to see this crisis as an opportunity. Again, thanks all the volunteers for Cov360. We're completely blessed by them. They've been incredible, and working together, it's brilliant."

Record of mishaps on WhatsApp

09/04/2020, 20:05 - Gian New Madrid: Likes on the way!!! P.s. someone is asking how can they join the event
 09/04/2020, 20:05 - Adam IE: <https://www.facebook.com/events/660385531406154/>
 09/04/2020, 20:05 - Adam IE: no?
 09/04/2020, 20:10 - H Ashish: yes
 09/04/2020, 20:10 - Gian New Madrid: Yep thanks, UK/cet problem
 09/04/2020, 20:19 - Ana Clara SL: I would like to know too. I am searching in the facebook page, but had no success in find it
 09/04/2020, 20:19 - Adam IE: facebook event page
 09/04/2020, 20:19 - Adam IE: <https://www.facebook.com/events/660385531406154/>
 09/04/2020, 20:19 - Adam IE: Still waiting for video to be activated I believe
 09/04/2020, 20:23 - H Ashish: Hello all, please join us using this link. <https://zoom.us/j/542345264>, thanks!
 09/04/2020, 20:23 - Roland UPG: It's on zoom
 09/04/2020, 20:25 - Ana Clara SL: thank you
 09/04/2020, 21:08 - Roland UPG: Very interesting discussion!!! I am actually enjoying it.
 09/04/2020, 21:11 - Adam IE: Theo - if you can see this - put in panel mode so can see everyone!
 09/04/2020, 21:11 - Adam IE: 🙏🙏
 09/04/2020, 21:13 - Annalisa SC: Great discussion!!

Does a panel need a host?

From the start ii

From Cov360 to closure

It really is the most global and local story event.
- Alex Erquicia

March 2020

The idea of Cov360 came and we started to build...

April 2020

The website and live launch of Cov360

November 2020

Obtained charitable status as a global NGO

January 2021

Launched the Pathfinders Programme

June 2021

Relaunch event as Public Health Pathways

August 2021

The Age of Public Health Magazine

January 2022

Finally got a bank account!

Yep, it's a marathon tale, but hey, silver lining – we scored a bank account!

February 2022

Began strategic support for Caafi Health

November 2022

Completed Pathfinders in Bristol

January 2023

Began strategic support for Daily Male

October 2023

Completed role in the SMILES project

December 2023

We declared victory at our AGM and began the unbuild

Knowing when to step back

We declared victory at our 2023 AGM

Pictured from left to right:

Taisiya Petukhova, Josh Entsminger, Alan Court, Lakshmi Sundaram, Philmon Habtai, K. Jade Robinson, Zoë Stockton, Adrian Holgate, Michael Baser, Theo Richardson-Gool.

Reflections from a few of the PHP cast:

What I have learned from the work with PHP is that we never waste time in working for the common good. The energy, time and resources allocated for this purpose will always come back at the best and appropriate time.

- Boris Mbia

Considering the impact of technology on different demographics, the PHP methodology of health research literacy is vital; it brings viewpoints together in an inclusive manner, building resilience in the community.

- Michael Baser

Always reflect at how far your initiative has come, because even though you may not see an impact immediately... years to come you will see and be grateful that you started.

- Jade Robinson

I love the fact that the organisation through its engagements emphasizes the importance of engaging people's experience or knowledge along research processes and working alongside communities and it's work.

- Nai Kalema

To step back, the charity turned to Lao Tzu:

‘Go to the people. Live with them. Learn from them. Start with what they know. Build with what they have. But with the best leaders, when the work is done, the task accomplished, the people will say, “We have done this ourselves.”’

Find an archived version of the Public Health Pathways website using this link:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20231101144917/https://publichealthpathways.org/>

Thank you for being with us on the journey. Closing the Charity: The story of Public Health Pathways (PHP). Please share generously.

A few numbers that show our process to bridge lived experience to build on the best science we know at the time.

The community: Over 60 volunteers. Over 30 countries. Over 30 languages.

Media output: Over 1,000,000 impressions. Over 500 posts. Over 50 reports. Over 20 videos.

Live events: Over 2,000 views. Over 10 live events, with over 20 event speakers.

Methodological legacy: Over 4 new or reinvented methodologies. Health Research Literacy around the Globe. Human-centred design. Systems thinking. Lay and Participatory Epidemiology.

Community legacy: Over 10 spin-out public health NGOs and companies started within the PHP community in over four countries over four years.

Thank you for being part of our story.

Our call to action: continue to shape a world where all generations can discover, create, and build healthier futures.

If you are curious about how we did it, we have two tips:

Firstly, we repeatedly reminded ourselves of the importance of the questions asked.

Levi-Strauss writes that the wise person 'doesn't give the right answer' [rather, they] 'pose the right questions'. Rumi goes further, 'look for the answer inside your question.' And Rilke invites us to, 'love the questions themselves.'

Secondly, and crucially, if you have questions about Public Health Pathways methodology to define inequalities and to co-create healthier futures, go and ask people with the lived experience of the former.

Start with listening to understand.

● ● ○ Public
● ○ ● Health
○ ● ● Pathways

2020
2024